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UNIVERSITY OF SAN FRANCISCO
UNIVERSITY CENTER, SAN FRANCISCO, CALIFORNIA 94117
ROBERT SWAIN, COORDINATOR

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CREATIVITY AND BRAIN MECHANISMS
Dr. Nouri Jaffar

The aim of this paper is to discuss the neural structure of the brain and its relationship to the creative process. It also presents the view that the striking differences in the intellectual levels and achievements of people are socio-historical in origin in the final analysis.

An intensive survey of the literature dealing with creativity, its nature and nurture, advanced by educationists and psychologists, has revealed radical differences in points of view concerning the interpretation of the nature of the creative process and of its cultivation. Some take their theoretical point of view from the psychological framework formulated by Galton and developed by Spearman and those who came after him ; they interpret the nature of creativity, and all mental processes, in terms of "intelligence" which is, in essence, a speculative concept, while ignoring its physical foundations.

~~For more information on the lecture please contact: nouri.jaffar@gmail.com~~

For more information on this paper:

Please contact World Council for Gifted and Talented Children at
<http://www.world-gifted.org>